

ASSESSMENT OF CONTENTS OF RECOMMENDED ECONOMICS TEXTBOOKS FOR SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

Yahya, Deborah Oreoluwa¹ⁱ,
Bosede Abimbola Adesina²

¹Department of Arts and Social Science Education,
Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

²PhD, Department of Arts and Social Science Education,
Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

Abstract:

The study examined the relevance of contents in the recommended Economics textbooks for senior secondary school students in Ogun State and examined the adequacy of contents in the recommended Economics textbooks. It also appraised the organization of contents in the recommended Economics textbooks. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population for the study comprised all the 14 Economics textbooks recommended by the Ogun State Ministry of Education for senior secondary school students in Ogun State. Four Economics textbooks among those recommended by the Ogun State Ministry of Education were selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. One research instrument was used for data collection namely; Economics Textbook Assessment Checklist (ETAC). The data were analyzed using frequency count and percentages. The result showed that the percentage relevance of the textbooks contents ranged from 42% to 66% (i.e 42%, 56%, 66% and 66%). The result also showed that the percentage adequacy of the textbooks contents ranged from 30% to 64% (i.e 30%, 62%, 62% and 64%). The study further revealed that the percentage organization of the textbooks contents ranged from 26% to 56% (i.e 26%, 43%, 56% and 56%). The study therefore concluded that the content relevance, adequacy and organization of the recommended Economics textbooks for senior secondary school students in Ogun State textbooks were not very high since none of the textbooks fell within the range of 81% to 100% in terms of what exists in the Economics curriculum.

Keywords: assessment, contents, recommended, economics textbooks, secondary school

ⁱ Correspondence: email yahyadeborah@gmail.com

1. Introduction

The introduction of Economics as a senior secondary school subject into the secondary school curriculum is hinged on the need to equip students with basic principles of Economics necessary for useful living and also to prepare and encourage students to be prudent and effective in the management of scarce resources. There is also a need for students to acquire basic knowledge and skills to appreciate the nature of economic problems in any society and adequately prepare them for the challenges in the Nigerian economy (NERDC, 2008). Economics plays a crucial role in the preparation of students for higher education.

Economics is one of the elective subjects to be studied at the secondary school level as prescribed by the National Policy on Education (NPE) (FGN, 2013). According to Adeyemi (2010), Economics is one of the elective subjects studied in senior secondary schools. Economics is a basic entry requirement for admission into Management and Social Science courses in Nigerian universities and colleges of education. As such, it is regarded as one of the most offered subjects by students in Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria (Yusuf, 2012). In order to determine whether the objectives for the teaching and learning of Economics are accomplished or not, achievement tests are conducted by teachers or public examination bodies such as the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO). The academic performance of students in Economics examinations conducted by WAEC in Nigeria is shown in the table below;

**Table 1: Students' Academic Performance in Economics
in the May/June WASSCE 2004-2014 in Nigeria**

Year	Entry Figure	No. and % of candidates who sat for Economics examination	No. and % of candidates with credits in Economics examination (A1-C6)	No. and % of candidates who had (D7-E8) in Economics examination	No. and % of candidates who failed Economics examination	No. and % of Absentees
2004	992,272	971,137 (97.87%)	372,995 (37.59%)	377,262 (38.02%)	220,880 (22.26%)	21,135 (2.13%)
2005	1,028,155	1,004,919 (97.74%)	372,603 (36.24%)	424,628 (41.30%)	207,687 (20.20%)	23,236 (2.26%)
2006	1,114,065	1,091,116 (97.94%)	550,905 (49.45%)	365,191 (32.78%)	175,020 (15.71%)	22,949 (2.06%)
2007	1,207,613	1,183,098 (97.97%)	461,903 (38.25%)	444,652 (36.82%)	276,543 (22.90%)	24,515 (2.03%)
2008	1,230,131	1,204,515 (97.92%)	592,939 (48.20%)	409,988 (33.33%)	201,588 (16.39%)	25,616 (2.08%)
2009	1,298,733	1,270,557 (97.83%)	577,345 (44.45%)	535,287 (41.22%)	157,925 (12.16%)	28,176 (2.17%)
2010	1,256,886	1,228,401 (97.73%)	690,949 (54.97%)	373,075 (29.68%)	164,377 (13.08%)	28,485 (2.27%)
2011	1,446,686	1,413,886	841,258	402,764	169,864	32,800

Yahya, Deborah Oreoluwa, Bosede Abimbola Adesina
ASSESSMENT OF CONTENTS OF RECOMMENDED ECONOMICS TEXTBOOKS
FOR SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

		(97.73%)	(58.15%)	(27.84%)	(11.74%)	(2.27%)
2012	1583775	1,540,902 (97.29%)	864,273 (54.57%)	444,308 (28.05%)	232,321 (14.67%)	42,873 (2.71%)
2013	1567942	1,532,194 (97.72%)	1,025,703 (65.42%)	346,564 (22.10%)	159,927 (10.20%)	35,748 (2.28%)
2014	1391186	1,363,994 (98.05%)	698,669 (50.22%)	362,863 (26.08%)	302,462 (21.74%)	27,192 (1.95%)

Source: WAEC Statistic Division, Yaba, Lagos (2014).

An observation of the students' performance in the West African Secondary School Certificate Examinations (WASSCE) in Economics as shown in table 1 reveals a fluctuating and low average students' performance. The credit pass rate was in the range of 36.24% to 65.42% (from 2004 to 2014) and an average of 48.93% of the candidates had ordinary passes and failure which are not useful for admission into higher institutions.

A lot of factors have been identified as the causes of this fluctuating and low trend in students' performance by the WAEC Chief Examiners in Economics at the end of the marking exercise in each year. They include: inadequate knowledge of the subject matter of Economics displayed by the students, poor presentation of relevant materials by the teachers, illegible handwriting, and scanty explanation of points, poor knowledge of drawing graphs, simple calculations, and inadequate preparation for the examinations by the students.

The WAEC Chief Examiners, while providing solutions to address the factors responsible for the students' low performance, suggested that students should read relevant and standard textbooks and not summaries and key points. Students should also acquaint themselves with basic economic terms. It was also recommended that students should also pay more attention to graphic analysis in Economics and also to the use of basic tools of economic analysis (WAEC Chief Examiners' Reports 2009 - 2014). Based on these suggestions, studies have been carried out in some states in order to look at the quality of Economics textbooks used in secondary schools but these studies are limited in scope because the studies assessed the recommended Economics textbooks using the WAEC Economics syllabus. As a result of this, there is still a need to assess the recommended Economics textbooks for students in Ogun state secondary schools.

2. Meaning, Nature and Scope of Economics

Economics is one of the elective subjects to be studied at secondary schools as prescribed by the nation's NPE (FGN, 2013). Economics as a social science subject is concerned with human behaviour such as how individuals earn their living and make choice between alternatives to satisfy their numerous wants. It focuses also on the study of firms and government whose activities are geared towards the production of goods and services for the satisfaction of human wants. Economics is generally defined as a

social science subject which studies human behaviour as a relationship between ends and scarce means which have alternative uses (Ande, 2012).

Economics as a social science analyzes the production, distribution, consumption of goods and services and the wellbeing of individual and the society at large. It explains how wealth is transferred to produce tangible goods, it also explains how people interact within markets to get what they want or accomplish certain goals. Since Economics is a driving force of human interaction, studying it often reveals why individuals, firms, households and the government behave in particular ways. Economics could be traced to the ancient Greek "oikonomia" (management of a household administration) from "oikos" (house) "nomos" (custom or law), hence "rules of the household". Political Economy was the earlier name for the subject, but economists in the late 19th century suggested "Economics" as a shorter term for "Economic Science" that was to also avoid a narrow political-interest connotation and as similar in form to Mathematics, Ethics and so forth. The focus of the subject is how economic agents behave or interact and how economies work (Tunde, 2002).

2.1 Concept of Textbook

The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2012), defined textbook as a book used in the study of a subject and as one containing a presentation of the principles of subject and a literary work relevant to the study of a subject. Textbook as one of the many resource materials used in schools is an educational input most consistently associated with gains in student learning. Textbooks contribute a vital part to the teaching-learning process in the school system and are used to convey learning experiences to the students (Iyawarun, 2009). Hence, the importance of quality textbooks in any field of education cannot be over-emphasized for the teachers and the students. Teachers also rely on textbooks to set the parameters of instruction and to facilitate the basic educational contents.

To this end, the possession of duly recommended quality textbooks in the hands of well trained teachers is a viable tool which, if used appropriately, could influence academic performance of students in the subject, as it will expose the learners to common learning experiences. Omebe (2014) opined that textbooks facilitate students' understanding of the topic discussed through the use of study questions and exercises provided in them. Students also use textbooks to obtain information, make observations, solve problems and arouse pleasure in reading. It can therefore be seen that quality textbooks play a great role in the teaching and learning process. However, in spite of the importance of textbooks in teaching and learning, the low average and fluctuating results in recent years in Economics examinations have been partly attributed to use of low standard textbooks.

2.2 Quality Textbooks

Quality textbooks play an important role in the educational development of any society. Quality textbook is also one of the learning resources that are consistently associated with gain in student learning. Particularly in developing countries, textbooks are the

primary conduits for delivering content knowledge to the students and teachers base their lesson plans on the material given in textbooks.

According to the Education Bureau (2009) main report, quality textbooks will possess the following:

- 1) compatibility with the aims/learning targets/objectives/guiding principles laid down in the curriculum guide/syllabus;
- 2) coverage of the core learning elements as specified in the curriculum guide/syllabus;
- 3) accuracy, clarity and relevance of information and data/concepts; and
- 4) appropriate and logical organisation of content/sequencing of concepts.

UNESCO (2010) also posited that textbooks content should be organized in a systematically progressive fashion as follows:

- 1) educational texts must be purposeful and structured, in progression order for the teaching-learning process;
- 2) the instruction should be structured, organized in chapters and in units;
- 3) the content of learning (information, explanations, comments, practical exercises, summaries, evaluation) must be presented in an orderly manner; and
- 4) there should be a systematic progression of learning towards the acquisition of new knowledge and learning new concepts, based on known items of knowledge.

2.3 Statement of Research Problem

It has been observed that students' performance in Economics examinations conducted by West African Examinations Council in recent years has been fluctuating and has recorded a low average. From previous studies, the problem has been partly attributed to teachers' poor content knowledge and pedagogical expertise (Jimoh, 2016), insufficiency of appropriate teaching aids and equipment, engagement of unqualified teaching personnel and use of low quality Economics textbooks by teachers and students. The assessment of the quality of Economics textbooks used had been carried out in some states but much has not been done in Ogun State. In addition, the few studies that have been carried out were limited in scope because the studies assessed the recommended Economics textbooks using the WAEC Economics syllabus. There is therefore the need to assess the quality of Economics textbooks in line with the National Economics curriculum in terms of relevance, adequacy and organization of contents.

2.4 Purpose of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. examine the relevance of contents in the recommended Economics textbooks in Ogun State senior secondary schools;
2. examine the adequacy of contents in the recommended Economics textbooks; and
3. appraise the organization of contents in the recommended Economics textbooks.

2.5 Research Questions

To achieve the objectives of the study, the following research questions were asked and answered;

- 1) To what extent are the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks in Ogun State relevant?
- 2) How adequate are the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks?
- 3) How organized are the contents of the textbooks?

3. Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for the study comprised the 14 recommended Economics textbooks by the Ministry of Education in Ogun State senior secondary schools. Four Economics textbooks among those recommended were selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. One research instrument titled "Economics Textbook Assessment Checklist (ETAC)" was used to elicit information on the relevance, adequacy and organization of contents. The ETAC was divided into three sections. The items in Sections A, B and C were adopted from Economics curriculum. Section A which consists of 48 items was used to elicit information about the selected textbooks contents relevance. Section B also consisted 48 items used to elicit information on the contents adequacy. Section C also consisted 48 items used to elicit information about the contents organization. Each item in Section A, B and C in the checklist was measured in degree ranging from "a great extent" to "not at all" on a scale equally ranging from 3-0. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages.

The textbooks assessed were represented with letters of the alphabets as shown below:

- A New Approach Economics;
- B Macmillan Mastering Economics for SSS;
- C Fundamentals of Economics for SSCE, NBCE, UTME;
- D Melrose Economics for SSS 1 – 3.

4. Results and Findings

Research Question 1: To what extent are the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks in Ogun State relevant?

In order to answer this research question, the contents of the national Economics curriculum and the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks were compared. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relevance of the Contents of Economics Textbooks
to the Economics Curriculum (SS 1, SS 2 and SS 3)

Textbooks	SS I		SS 2		SS 3		Total
	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	
A	32	71	48	89	15	33	95 (66%)
B	21	47	25	46	14	31	60 (42%)
C	28	62	50	93	17	38	95 (66%)
D	29	64	37	69	15	33	81 (56%)

Key: Freq = Frequency, Percent = Percentage, 0%-20% = Very Low, 21%-40% = Low, 41%-60% = Moderate, and 61%-80% = High, 81%-100% = Very High.

From Table 2, findings of the study showed that the contents of textbooks A(New Approach Economics) and C(Fundamentals of Economics for SSCE, NBCE, UTME) had the highest percentage relevance of 66% and 66% respectively. This shows that the relevance of contents of textbook A and C is high to the Economics curriculum. The results also indicated that textbook B (Macmillian Mastering Economics for SSS) had the least percentage of 42%, which can be interpreted to have a moderate relevance to the Economics curriculum. Based on the table, the textbooks can be ranked as A (66%), C (66%), D (56%) and B (42%) in terms of their content relevance. This finding is in agreement with Olatunji (2016) and Alani (2015) whose work showed that the extent of relevance of contents in some of the Economics textbooks and Physics textbooks is not very high.

Research Question 2: How adequate are the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks?

To answer this research question, the contents of the national Economics curriculum and the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks were compared in order to determine the adequacy. The results are presented in Tables 3.

Table 3: Adequacy of the Contents of Economics Textbooks to
the Economics Curriculum (SS 1, SS 2 and SS 3)

Textbooks	SS I		SS 2		SS 3		Total
	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	
A	31	69	46	85	15	33	92 (64%)
B	16	36	18	33	9	20	43 (30%)
C	27	60	46	85	16	36	89 (62%)
D	24	53	35	65	13	29	72 (50%)

From Table 3, the result showed that the contents of textbook A (New Approach Economics) had the highest percentage of 64%. This shows that the contents adequacy of textbook A is high in relation to the Economics curriculum. The results also indicated that textbook B (Macmillian Mastering Economics for SSS) had the least percentage of 30%, which can be interpreted to have a low level of adequacy in relation to the Economics curriculum. Based on the table, the textbooks can be ranked as A (64%), C (62%), D (62%) and B (30%), in terms of their contents adequacy.

Research Question 3: How organized are the contents of the textbooks?

In order to determine how organized the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks are in relation to the national Economics curriculum, the contents of the national Economics curriculum and the contents of the recommended Economics textbooks were compared in order to determine the organization. The results are presented in Tables 4.

Table 4: Organization of the Contents of Economics Textbooks to the Economics Curriculum (SS 1, SS 2 and SS 3)

Textbooks	SS I		SS 2		SS 3		Total
	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	Freq (f)	Percent (%)	
A	28	62	38	70	15	33	81 (56%)
B	15	33	13	24	9	20	37 (26%)
C	24	53	40	74	17	38	81 (56%)
D	23	51	22	41	17	38	62 (43%)

From Table 4, the result showed that the contents of textbook A (New Approach Economics) and textbook C (Fundamentals of Economics for SSCE, NBCE, UTME) had the highest percentage of 56% and 56% respectively. This shows that the contents of textbook A and C is moderately organized in relation to the Economics curriculum. The results also indicated that textbook B (Macmillian Mastering Economics for SSS) had the least percentage of 26%, which can be interpreted to have a low level of organization in relation to the Economics curriculum. Based on the table, the textbooks can be ranked as A (56%), C (56%), D (43%) and B (26%).The finding agrees with the study of Alani (2015) whose studies recommended that contents of the Physics textbooks should be arranged according to classes for easy clarification as stated in the Physics curriculum.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that none of the Economics textbooks’ content relevance, adequacy and organization were very high in terms of what exists in the Economics curriculum. The percentage relevance of the textbooks contents fell within the level of moderate to high relevance and the contents adequacy fell within the level of low to high contents adequacy. The percentage organization of the textbooks contents fell within the level of low to moderate content organization. This may have an adverse effect on the students’ performance in external examinations.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. All the textbooks should be revised to have contents on theme IX (Business Finance) for SSS I and theme I (Comparative Economics), theme II (Population, Labour Market and Human Capital Development), theme IV (Financial Institutions and Regulatory Agencies), theme VIII (Applied Economics and Contemporary Economic Organizations) for SSS III.

2. Contents of the textbooks should be organized according to classes as specified in the Economics curriculum. This gives room for better understanding of those topics that are repeated across the three classes.

References

- Education Bureau. (2009). Working group on textbooks and e-learning resources. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/m?q=compatibility+with+the+aims%2Flearning+targets%2Fobjectives%2Fguiding+principles+laid+down+in+the+curriculum+guide%2Fsyllabus> on 25/11/2016
- Iyawarun, B. (2009). *Method for teaching skills approach*. Columbus Ohio: Chalse E. Merrill.
- Merriam-Webster Dictionary (7th edition), (2012). Retrieved from <http://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/textbook> on 5/3/2016
- National Policy on Education (2013). *Federal Republic of Nigeria* (6th edition). Abuja: NERDC press.
- Nigeria Educational Research Development Council (NERDC), (2008). *Senior secondary school Economics curriculum*. Lagos: NERDC.
- Omebe C.A. (2014). Evaluation of topical coverage and study questions of approved Integrated Science textbooks in Ebonyi State junior secondary schools. Ebonyi State. *University Journal of Education and Practice*. 2(1), 82-84.
- Robbins, L. (1935). *An Essay on the nature and significance of Economic Science*. London: Macmillan and Co.
- Tunde S. (2002). *Economics for senior secondary schools*. Ikeja: Nelson Publishers Ltd.
- West African Examination Council (2009). *May/June 2012 WASSCE Chief Examiners' Report on Economics*. Lagos, Nigeria: WAEC.
- West African Examination Council (2010). *May/June 2012 WASSCE Chief Examiners' Report on Economics*. Lagos, Nigeria: WAEC.
- West African Examination Council (2011). *May/June 2012 WASSCE Chief Examiners' Report on Economics*. Lagos, Nigeria: WAEC.
- West African Examination Council (2012). *May/June 2012 WASSCE Chief Examiners' Report on Economics*. Lagos, Nigeria: WAEC.
- Yusuf, K. (2012). Effective teaching of Economics in senior secondary school. *West African Journal of Education*. 1(1),9-13.
- United Nations Educational Science and Cultural Organization Regional Bureau for Education in Africa. (2010). *Education for all in Africa bulletin, Technical report, UNESCO*. Retrieved from: http://www.dakar.unesco.org/efa/bulletin/index_en.shtml on 6/8/2016

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).